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FACTORS AFFECTING LOYALTY OF CUSTOMERS TOWARD INTERNET SERVICE COMPANIES (EMPIRICAL STUDY IN AMMAN CITY)

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to study the factors affecting the loyalty of customers toward internet service companies in Amman city; these factors namely, service quality, trust, commitment, satisfaction, and after-sale service.

Data were collected through questionnaires forming a representative sample. A total of 460 questionnaires were distributed to internet users in Amman city, the findings indicated that there is a positive relationship between satisfaction, service quality, trust, commitment, and after-sale service with customer loyalty. After-sales service was found to be the most critical factor in affecting customer loyalty.

Keywords: *Customer Satisfaction, Service Quality, Trust, Commitment, After-sale service, Customer Loyalty.*

1. Introduction

Customer Loyalty research in services is an important area in the field of marketing, studies conducted in the financial services industry show that increasing customer retention (or customer loyalty) by 5 percent could lead to 25-75 percent profit growth (Bowen and Chen, 2001). Customer loyalty is one of the most important aspects of marketing planning since retain customer is more important than customer attracting (Behara et al., 2002). Internet services have become very essential in today's world. This is due to rapid technological innovations which allow people to communicate with each other anywhere and at any time. Nowadays, there is a fierce competition among leading internet services companies with each other to become a main company (Vesel and Zabkar, 2009). Further, to attain the basic business goals of survival and growth, business investment are looking for ways to attract and retain customers in the long run. As competition is increasing among the internet service companies in Amman city, it is essential for the internet service companies to know about their customers' perception on service quality, trust commitment and satisfaction and service after sale that play a basic role in choosing the internet service company. Therefore, customer loyalty is a basic and important when consumers have been connected to the internet service sector. This research has applied 5 hypotheses and 6 variables to explore the customer loyalty towards an internet service companies in Amman city. The variables applied in this research are satisfaction, Service quality, trust, commitment, after-sale service and customer loyalty

2. Research Objectives

The objectives of this research can be summarized as follows:

1. To determine the relationship between satisfaction and customer loyalty toward internet service companies in Amman city.
2. To determine the relationship between service quality and customer loyalty toward internet service companies in Amman city.

3. To determine the relationship between trust and customer loyalty toward internet service companies in Amman city.
4. To determine the relationship between commitment and customer loyalty toward internet service companies in Amman city.
5. To determine the relationship between after-sale service and customer loyalty toward internet service companies in Amman city.

3. Research problems

This research paper tries to answer these questions:

- 1-What is the relationship between satisfaction and customer loyalty?
- 2-What is the relationship between service quality and customer loyalty?
- 3-What is the relationship between trust and customer loyalty?
- 4-What is the relationship between commitment and customer loyalty?
- 5-What is the relationship between after-sale service and customer loyalty?

4. Importance of Research

This research attempts to concentrate on the impressions being held by customers toward internet service companies in Amman city, and also to know the factors that lead to customer retention, and do not turn them to another internet service company. And gives specific indicators for internet service companies in Amman city for the most important factors that will help them to reach customer loyalty. This helps them to increase profit.

The research paper illustrate in general the level of customer loyalty toward internet service companies in Amman city which will help the marketing managers to improve the quality of internet service provided by the companies within the intense competition in the internet service. .

5. Literature Review

5.1 Customer loyalty

Oliver (1999) has defined loyalty of customer as deeply held commitment to repurchase or repeat a preferred product consistently in the future, in spite of situational effect and marketing efforts having the prospect to cause shift behavior. Customer loyalty is well- considered to be a function of satisfaction and that loyal customers give a share in organization profitability by consumer spending on company products, repurchase, and by recommending the organization to other consumers (Bowen & Chen, 2001). Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that the switching barrier plays the role of an adjustment factor in the mutual relations between satisfied customer and customer loyalty. In other words, when the level of customer satisfaction is identical, the level of loyalty of customer can vary depend on the great size of the switching barrier (Colgate, M., and Lang. B. (2001)

5.2 Satisfaction

According to Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V., & Berry, L. (1985), to create excellent value constantly for a buyer requires that a provider understood the buyer's whole value chain. Attributes that stimulate a customer's

foremost purchase may vary from the criterion later. Brown, Tom J., Gilbert A. Churchill, Jr., and J. Paul Peter (1993) has defined customer satisfaction as the case in which customer needs, wants and expectations during the product or service's lifetime are met or exceeded resulting in repurchase, loyalty and favorable word-of-mouth. (Kotler, 2009) defined customer satisfaction in many ways, in general it's related to a customer's overall evaluation of expectancy and experience. Satisfaction is another leading effect which should be taken into account when forming the overall customer loyalty towards their service suppliers. In banks, the customers ask themselves about the level of the services and decide about the lack of importance given to them and decide about repeat purchase behavior after usage of the services. Satisfaction level is always high when the customer gives minimal price and gets maximum of usage and profit (Jamal and Kamal, 2004)

5.3 Service Quality

Service quality is a concept that has aroused considerable interest and debate in the research literature because of the difficulties in both defining it and measuring it with no overall consensus emerging on either. Most of the researches have shown that high service quality contributes significantly to profitability. Vavra (1994) has defined service quality as the consistently delivering products and services that fully meet the needs and expectations of the customer. Another definition by Ueno (2010) the authors consider the service quality gaps model as the conceptualization of service quality as the gap between expected service and perceived service.

American Marketing Association has defined service as the activities or bundle of benefits offered for sale or offered associated with specific product. Kotler & Armstrong (2004) defined service as any activity or benefit provided by one party to another party which is basically intangible and does not lead to any ownership. Zeithaml et al. (1996). The existence of a relation between service quality and customer keeping at a high level marks that quality of service has an effect on consumer behavior, where superior quality of service leads to proper behavioral intentions (i.e. loyalty of service), and while unfavorable behavioral intentions are an outcome of inferior quality of service.

5.4 Trust

Trust is more difficult to build and even more critical for success in the service sector. Trust is a long-term proposition that may be tough to build and easy to lose. According to Rauyruen and Miller (2007), there are two levels of trust. Consumers' trust in one specified salesperson is at the first level. Whereas at the second level trust is in the organization. If trusts occur, then it is obvious that the person is likely to buy something. According to Morgan and Hunt (1994), relationships can be viewed as a set of transactions that foster an awareness of a shared relationship through trust and commitment. High level of trust and commitment in turn are related to high level of customer keeping, and this leads to high profit of the organization. A consumer will wish a relation with a specified business if he finds the benefits received to exceed the effort in obtaining benefits. From this it is evident that both parties in the relationship have certain costs or effort, but also expect benefits (Rootman 2006).

Trust is well-considered as the most important variable to build long-term relations, for it enhances loyalty of the customer. Bolton et al (2000) has highlighted that loyalty rewarding programs have a positive effect on customers' evaluation and behavior. These loyalty programs help in raising the period and usage levels. Customer satisfaction is the key to customer keeping. Discontented customers will turn over to other services.

5.5 Commitment

Rauyruen and Miller (2007) have defined commitment as a psychological affection of the mind through which an attitude concerning continuation of a relationship with a business partner is formed. Relationships are built on the foundation of mutual commitment, and the level of commitment is found to be the powerful predictor of the elective decision to follow up a relationship (Liang & Wang, 2005). Customers who are committed to a relationship might have a greater propensity to act because of their need to remain consistent with their

commitment (Liang & Wang 2005). More committed customers tend to form a positive overall impression of the total duration of the relationship, including different transactions, positive and negative, and these customers exhibit strong intentions to stay in the relationship (Chaudhuri and Holbrook, 2001). In the relationship context, commitment is considered as an enduring desire to maintain a valued relationship.

5.6 after-sale service

(Vavra, 1995) mention that after-sales service include servicing, repair, and upgrading. If these services can be given at a constant or ensured price, they could be a worthy competitive tool. In servicing, it is to be mention that one way of solving the repair problem is to have defect-free products and then service can be bundled into the product price, which can also be of significance value. The approach of Mathe and Shapiro (1993) looks for increased overall efficiency between the supplier and customer. Service activities are defined at the design phase.

After- sales service may not be profitable on its own, but is frequently a key determinant in the sale of the product itself. It has been estimated that the importance of services will grow in the future. As a term, “after-sales services” has been used the most, to describe services that are provided to the customer after the products have been delivered (Vitasek, 2005).

6. Research Framework

Most of the previous empirical studies provided evidence. In the theoretical frame work, customer loyalty, as dependent variable, is affected by five independent variables; satisfactions, service quality, trust, commitment, and service after sale.

The framework of the study shown in Figure (1) there were five hypotheses formulated based on the framework and they are shown as follows:

Hypothesis 1: There is statically significant relationship between Satisfaction and customer loyalty.

Hypothesis 2: There is statically significant relationship between service quality and customer loyalty.

Hypothesis 3: There is statically significant relationship between trust and customer loyalty.

Hypothesis 4: There is statically significant relationship between commitment and customer loyalty.

Hypothesis 5: There is statically significant relationship between after-sale service and customer loyalty.

Figure (1)

7. Research Methodology

This research involved a survey of internet services users in Amman city. The research methodology will address these topics are research design, population; sample size and sample method, hypothesis of the research, questionnaires design, analysis method and result of reliability.

This research will focus on factors that effecting customer loyalty toward internet service companies such as service quality, trust, commitment, satisfaction and after-sales service. For that proposed five hypotheses to determine the relationship between the different factors and customer loyalty, also considered customer loyalty as a dependent factor, on the other hand service quality, satisfaction, trust, commitment, and after-sales service as an independents factors.

The questionnaires were pre-tested with 20 users of internet service companies in Amman city. The purpose of the research was explained to the internet service users to simplify feedback, answering user's questions. Some participants suggested that a few words in the questions somewhat not visible. Except for these comments, the result of pre-test specified that, questions are realistic, accurate, and easy to understand. After the pre-test, unclear words and sentences were revised.

The research population consists of all internet services users in Amman city. In addition, there were 460 questionnaires distributed to internet services users in Amman city, however, only 421 questionnaires obtained have valid responses and were used for data analysis in this research paper. According to Sekaran (2003), 421 responses are considered as an acceptable number for researchers to proceed with data analysis.

To draw a representative sample, a convenience sample was chosen; Convenience samples are the most common form of sampling design in social science research (Mohr, 1990) and provide researchers with an acceptable database to use statistical inference techniques. This approach to sampling design is also applicable in services marketing.

There are two main parts in the questionnaires, the first part- the demographic factors of the participants. These factors are: gender, age, education, and income. The second part of the questionnaires is about the dependent factor - loyalty of customer, on the other hand five independent factors- service quality, trust, commitment, satisfaction and service after sale. There are 23 questions in this part; therefore, this research used a Likert scale to measure independent and dependent factors since this format is widely used in both marketing and social science (Burns & Bush, 2002). However, many researchers argued that using a five-point format is good as any other Churchill, G., & Lacobucci, D. (2004). For the reason that it minimizes disruption to the participants.

8. Reliability

The reliabilities for the variables were calculated and all concur with Nunnally's (1978) minimum threshold of 0.70. Table.1, lists the Cronbach's Alpha (coefficient alpha) of each factor. All the factors show a high degree of reliability. Table: 1. show that there were five independent factors and one dependent factor of customer loyalty that was examined by the researcher.

Table 1: Reliability

Variables	Number of Item	Cronbach Alpha
Satisfaction	5	0.856
Quality	6	0.878
Trust	4	0.868
Commitment	4	0.813
Services after sale	4	0.859
Loyalty	4	0.859
All performance		0.868

9. Findings

9.1 Demographic variables

Table (2) below show that there were slightly more of male respondents (54.2%) than female (45.8%). The respondents belongs to the age group between 26 years old and 35 years old (48.2%). Respondents who possess a bachelor degree (26.6) or diploma are (18.3%). Moreover, 14% of the respondents are from the group with incomes less than 300 JD and 301- 500 JD (13.4%).

Table 2: Summary of respondent characteristics

Characteristics	Title	Frequencies	Percentage
Gender	Male	228	54.2%
	Female	193	45.8%
Age	Less than 25 years	153	36.3%
	26-35 years	203	48.2%
	36-45 years	38	9%
	More than 46 years	27	6.4%
Education	Secondary School	92	14.2%
	Diploma	119	18.3%
	Bachelor	175	26.6%
	Graduated	36	5.5%
Income	Less than 300JD	91	14%
	301-500JD	87	13.4%
	501-700JD	57	8.8%
	700-900JD	63	9.7%
	900-1100JD	59	9.1%
	More than 1101JD	64	9.85

9.2 Correlation analysis

Correlation analysis describes the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables (Pallant, 2001) and the degree of correlation indicates the strength and importance of a relationship between them. The correlation between these six factors is shown in Table 3. The correlation is considered a high and moderate correlation based on Cohen (1988), and Pallant (2007) more than .50 score is considered largely correlated and more than 0.3 is moderate correlatin between variables.

Table3: Correlation analysis

		Satisfaction	Quality	Trust	Commitment	Services after sale	Loyalty
Correlation	Satisfaction	1.000					
	Quality	.694**	1.000				
	Trust	.450**	.599**	1.000			
	Commitment	.472**	.537**	.620**	1.000		
	Services after sale	.429**	.533**	.525**	.535**	1.000	
	Loyalty	.436**	.505**	.497**	.425**	.601**	1.000

** . Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

9.3 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was performed for getting answers of research questions of this study. In order to conduct multiple regression analysis, some assumptions of the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables need to be met such as normality, linearity, constant variance of the error terms and independence of the error terms (Hair et al., 1998).

Table 4: Multiple Regression Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.834	.164		5.086	.000
	Satisfaction	.109	.052	.110	2.105	.036
	Quality	.113	.059	.113	1.920	.025
	Trust	.170	.051	.173	3.305	.001
	Commitment	.016	.053	-.015	-.295	.000
	Services after sale	.383	.044	.411	8.646	.000

9.4 Simple regression

Simple regression analysis shows the contribution of each variable on the customer loyalty.

Based on the table (5) the customer satisfaction R² is 0.436, that mean the customer satisfaction has an effect and contribute on customer loyalty toward the internet companies by 43.6%. Quality of service R² is 0.255, which mean it has an effect and contribute on customer loyalty toward the internet companies by 25.5%. trust R² is 0.247, it has an effect and contribute on customer loyalty toward the internet companies by 24.7%. commitment R² is 0.425, it has an effect and contribute on customer loyalty toward the internet companies by 42.5%. and services after the sale R² is 0.51, it has an effect and contribute on customer loyalty toward the internet companies by 51.1%. That means most critical factor on customer loyalty toward internet service companies.

Table 5: Simple regression

Variables	R ²
Customer Satisfaction	0.436
Quality of Services	0.255
Trust	0.247
Commitment	0.425
Services after the sale	0.51

10. Hypothesis test

The results of Hypothesis 1 the data indicate satisfaction value is significantly and positively related to loyalty of customer for the total sample (Beta=.109, p=.036),the data shows that service quality is significantly and positively related to customer loyalty for the total sample (Beta=.113, p=.025). Therefore, the results support Hypothesis 2. Regarding Hypothesis 3, the data indicate that trust is significantly related to customer loyalty for the total sample (Beta=.170, p=.001). Therefore, the results support Hypothesis 3. The findings of Hypothesis 4 indicate that commitment is significantly and positively related to loyalty of customer for the total sample (Beta=.016, p=.000). Therefore, the results support Hypothesis 4. Finally, the findings of Hypothesis 5, The results of Hypothesis5 shows that after-sales service is significantly and positively related to customer loyalty for the total sample (Beta=.383, p=.000).

11. Conclusion

This research examined the relationship between customer loyalty as a dependent variable and satisfaction, service quality, trust, commitment, and after-sales service as independent variables.

At the end, the data which has been collected was analyzed by correlation and regression analysis. Results indicate that all factors are vital and have positive effects on customer loyalty toward internet service companies in Amman city.

In addition to that customer loyalty can be a worthy factor that helps developing and improving companies' performances which directly leads to increase profits in the long-term; this research paper also proposed and justified the theoretic framework to explain customer loyalty in particular, in the case of Internet service companies in Amman city. Moreover, objectives and questions of the research were answered and confirmed by the finding of the research. Additional factors are still recommended to be included and tested on a larger scale in future research which is related to customer loyalty.

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